

MICROSTRUCTURE AND MATERIAL CHARACTERIZATION OF BAT WING TISSUE FOR ACTIVE SKIN COMPOSITES

N. Goulbourne¹, * Y. Wang¹, S. Son², A. Skulborstad¹

¹ Aerospace Engineering, University of Michigan, Ann Arbor, USA ² Mechanical Engineering, Virginia Tech, Blacksburg, USA

*(ngbourne@umich.edu)

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1 Introduction

Bat skins have an inherent microstructure yielding specific macroproperties that enable unique flight style and aerodynamic footprint. It is based on this key observation that we have undertaken the first systematic study of bat skins to investigate its material properties commensurate with specific behaviors and functionality. Given the multifunctional quality of bat skins: water-proofing, gas exchange, thermo-regulation, load-bearing airfoils, an array of airflow receptors, touch sensors, food-trapping, to name a few, it is ultimately a challenge to isolate those specific membrane properties that are integral to flight maneuvers. Investigating the mechanics of bat skins specifically in relation to first their macroproperties and ideally their microstructure is one of the novel discriminators of this research that could provide a major advancement towards designing synthetic skins for artificial bat flight. In this presentation, we highlight our initial findings as to the microstructure and material behavior of bat wing skins.

2 Material Characterization and Model

2.1 Material Properties

Understanding the role that tissue structure plays in rendering specific mechanical properties and macroscopic functionality will provide a template for developing synthetic materials in bio-mimicry. Structurally based constitutive models can offer insight into the functions and mechanics of each tissue component. For most soft biological tissues, including arterial walls and skin tissue, the main load-carrying constituent is presumed to be the distributed collagen fibers, which are embedded in an isotropic base matrix, composed of ground substance. It is believed that the organization of the collagen fibers (micron length scale) gives rise to the

anisotropy of the material [1]. Motivated by histology information of the wing membrane of the bat, a statistical treatment is formulated in this paper to capture the effect of the distribution of fiber cross-sectional area *and* the distribution of the number of fibers, which has not been done before.

2.2 Constitutive Model

We present a generalized statistical treatment to model tissues containing more than one dispersive fiber property for the first time [2]. The work is motivated by observations in bat wing tissue of two orthogonally aligned families of fiber bundles, with prominent differences in fiber diameters and fiber spacing [3]. The diameter of the fiber bundle varies dramatically with fiber orientation even within each family. As a result, the previously proposed fiber density function, which only accounts for the number of fibers in different direction, is not sufficient to represent the overall anisotropy of the material. Here, a statistical treatment (Von Mises distribution) is applied to integrate two distributed properties – 1) the number of fibers and 2) the fiber cross-sectional area in different directions – into one effective fiber density function.

For two families of fibers, the anisotropic strain energy function W is of the following form:

$$W(\mathbf{F}, \mathbf{a}_{01}, \mathbf{a}_{01}) = W(I_1, I_2, I_3, I_4, I_5, I_6, I_7, I_8, I_9), \quad (1)$$

where F is the deformation gradient, the fiber orientations are \mathbf{a}_{01} and \mathbf{a}_{02} , and I_i are the stretch invariants. The nine invariants are

$$I_1 = \text{tr } \mathbf{C}, \quad I_2 = \frac{1}{2}[(\text{tr } \mathbf{C})^2 - \text{tr } \mathbf{C}^2], \quad I_3 = \det \mathbf{C},$$

$$I_4 = \mathbf{C} : (\mathbf{a}_{01} \otimes \mathbf{a}_{01}), \quad I_5 = \mathbf{C}^2 : (\mathbf{a}_{01} \otimes \mathbf{a}_{01}), \quad I_6$$

$$I_8 = (\mathbf{a}_{01} \cdot \mathbf{a}_{02}) \mathbf{a}_{01} \cdot \mathbf{C} \mathbf{a}_{02}, \quad I_9 = (\mathbf{a}_{01} \cdot \mathbf{a}_{02})^2. \quad (2)$$

For biological materials reinforced by two families of fibers, the strain energy function may be split into two parts. One part is associated with isotropic deformations, denoted by W_{iso} , and the other part associated with anisotropic deformations, denoted by W_{aniso} . Since the collagen fibers, which are presumed to be the main load-carrying constituent at a higher strain, are not activated in the lower range of the strain, W_{iso} is only associated with the base matrix and W_{aniso} with collagen fibers. Therefore,

$$W = W_{iso}(\mathbf{F}) + W_{aniso}(\mathbf{F}, \mathbf{a}_{01}, \mathbf{a}_{02}). \quad (3)$$

Notice that I_9 in Equation 7 is a constant. Also, because most biological tissues may be considered incompressible, I_3 and J are also constants with the value of 1. To further simplify the formulation, as in Holzapfel *et al.* 2000, we exclude the isotropic invariants $-I_1$ and I_2 , the invariants associated with $\mathbf{C}^2 - I_5$ and I_7 , and also I_8 from the anisotropic part of the strain energy function. Thus,

$$W = W_{iso}(I_1, I_2) + W_{aniso}(I_4, I_6). \quad (4)$$

It is worth pointing out that I_4 and I_6 have specific physical meanings, each representing the square of the stretch ratios in the direction of \mathbf{a}_{01} and \mathbf{a}_{02} , respectively.

In previous studies, fibers of the same type (collagen or elastin) are treated as having the same stiffness. Therefore, the number of fibers in a certain direction is sufficient to describe the stiffness of the material in that direction. As a result, the constructed fiber density function proposed by Lanir, Gasser and Holzapfel only counts the number of fibers in different orientations. However, in some tissues, it has been observed that the fiber or fiber bundle diameters vary significantly with fiber orientation within each family [3,4]. This introduces a second distributed parameter that should be incorporated in the formulation. To model these characteristics, the fiber density function obtained by Holzapfel *et al* is modified [6]. In this framework, all the fiber bundles in the same family are treated as the same

type but the stiffness of each bundle is proportional to its cross-sectional area. Thus, the modified fiber density function $\bar{\rho}(\phi)$ is defined later in Equation 37 such that $\bar{\rho}(\phi)d\phi$ will represent the fraction of the total bundle stiffness in the direction between ϕ and $\phi + d\phi$.

The average bundle cross-sectional area at different orientations is considered as a function of its orientation. Similar to the original fiber density function, we introduce a normalized average cross-sectional area distribution function modeled as a π -periodic Von Mises distribution for each family of fiber bundles. We derive the new invariant for one family of fibers in this section.

It is usually sufficient to use a Neo-Hookean model for the isotropic part of the strain energy function associated with the ground substance in most cases (Holzapfel & Ogden 2010). For the anisotropic part, similar to the motivation under Fung's model, exponential functions are chosen in a phenomenological sense to capture the stiffening effect mentioned above. Therefore, we obtain,

$$W_{iso}(I_1) = \frac{c}{2}(I_1 - 2), \quad (5)$$

$$W_{aniso}(I_4, I_6) = \frac{k_1}{2\gamma_1} \{\exp[\gamma_1(I_4 - 1)^2] - 1\} + \frac{k_2}{2\gamma_2} \{\exp[\gamma_2(I_6 - 1)^2] - 1\}, \quad (6)$$

where c and k_i ($i=1, 2$) are material parameters, while γ_i ($i=1, 2$) are dimensionless parameters which will affect the shape of the stress-strain curve.

We derive a new structure tensor \mathbf{H} and a new invariant

$$\mathbf{H} = \bar{\kappa} \mathbf{I} - \bar{\kappa} (\mathbf{n} \otimes \mathbf{n}) + (1 - 2\bar{\kappa}) \mathbf{a}_\mu \otimes \mathbf{a}_\mu, \quad (7)$$

$$I_{4\mu}^* = \bar{\kappa} I_1 - \bar{\kappa} \lambda_3^2 + (1 - 2\bar{\kappa}) I_{4\mu}, \quad (8)$$

where the modified dispersion parameter $\bar{\kappa}$ and modified invariant $I_{4\mu}$ are

$$\bar{\kappa} = \int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} \bar{\rho}(\phi) \sin^2(\phi) d\phi, \quad (44)$$

$$I_{4\mu} = (\mathbf{a}_\mu \otimes \mathbf{a}_\mu) : \mathbf{C}.$$

The fiber distribution $\rho(\phi)$ is initially aligned about the original dominant fiber angle 0° . The area

distribution is given by $\rho_a(\phi)$ aligned about ϕ_a , the angle with the largest diameter fibers. The distribution of cross-sectional areas is described by

$$\rho_a(\phi) = \frac{\exp(a \cos 2(\phi - \phi_a))}{I^0(a)}, \quad (36)$$

where ϕ_a is the fiber angle with the largest cross-sectional area, a is the concentration factor for the area distribution and ϕ is between $-\pi/2$ and $\pi/2$. For illustration purposes, a plot of the area distribution for various values of a are presented in Fig. 1 for a dominant fiber area angle $\phi_a = 40^\circ$. The modified

fiber density function $\bar{\rho}(\phi) = \frac{1}{n} \rho_a(\phi) \rho(\phi)$

produces a shift of the fiber density function to the right. There arises a new effective dominant fiber angle μ . Note that the invariant $I_{4,\mu}$ is associated with the new dominant fiber angle μ . Substituting new dispersion factors and invariants into Equation 6, we obtain the newly proposed strain energy function for biological tissues reinforced by two families of dispersed fibers with spatially-varying properties

$$\begin{aligned} W &= W_{iso} + W_{aniso} \\ &= \frac{c}{2}(I_1 - 3) + \frac{k_1}{2\gamma_1} \{ \exp[\gamma_1(\bar{\kappa}_1 I_1 - \bar{\kappa}_1 \lambda_3^2 + (1 - 2\bar{\kappa}_1)I_{4,\mu} - 1)] - 1 \} \\ &\quad + \frac{k_2}{2\gamma_2} \{ \exp[\gamma_2(\bar{\kappa}_2 I_1 - \bar{\kappa}_2 \lambda_3^2 + (1 - 2\bar{\kappa}_2)I_{6,\mu} - 1)] - 1 \}. \end{aligned}$$

The anisotropy of the material is captured by a general structure tensor derived specifically for planar fiber distributions. The general structure tensor for planar fiber distribution is constructed within a 3-dimensional space, which shows consistence with previous work as expected. The current approach, however, is more adaptable to more general cases when the fiber distribution is planar and anisotropic since Gasser's formulation is only valid for planar isotropic cases [7]. Based on the assumption that fiber stiffness is linearly proportional to the fiber cross-sectional area and that the fiber cross-sectional area is a function of the fiber angle, a statistical treatment is applied to integrate the effect of two distributed fiber properties. This leads to new dominant fiber orientations and dispersion factors. A set of numerical simulations

show that the contribution of the fiber area distribution is significant in describing the material's anisotropy. The fiber cross-sectional area distribution can either enhance or reduce the anisotropy of the material depending on its dominant orientation, dispersion factor and the original fiber distribution. It should be pointed out that this framework can be used for modeling the integrated effect of any two distributed fiber properties. The formulation is only applicable for distribution functions that depend on the fiber angle. Also, the model assumes that fiber stiffness is linearly proportional to the fiber cross-sectional area, and lacks coupling terms to account for interactions between fiber and matrix. Furthermore, the model cannot distinguish between n number of fibers and the bulk fiber equivalent.

A simulation of the biaxial response of a biological membrane using the newly developed strain energy function is shown in Fig. 2. The results illustrate the fact that the fiber diameter distributions in addition to the fiber angle distribution greatly affect the predicted anisotropy.

2.3 Biaxial Characterization Tests

Biaxial tests on bat wing tissue were carried out using a specialized test setup in our laboratory. The strain results in the chord-wise and span-wise directions indicating drastic anisotropy are shown in Fig. 2. The highly complex structure of the wing skin has led to the development of a new technique in our laboratory: Polarized Image Correlation (PIC) for Sub-Surface Microscale Deformation Measurements. This technique is a full field non-invasive real-time visualization of deformations at the microscale. Figure 2 shows a screen-capture of the sub-surface fiber-tracking using digital image correlation DIC.

3 Summary

A semi-structural continuum model is presented for bat wing tissue. A new fiber density function is defined, which accounts for the spatial variation of more than one distributed property. A statistical treatment is applied to the standard fiber density function [1] to integrate the effect of two distributed

fiber properties. This leads to new dominant fiber orientations and dispersion factors. A set of numerical simulations shows that the contribution of the fiber area distribution is significant to the material's anisotropy. A new experimental technique is developed to visualize sub-surface deformations of these complex materials. Two novel material concepts based on our studies of the wing tissue will be described in the presentation.

Fig. 1. Statistical distribution of fiber area in the tissue as a function of angle.

Fig. 2. Anisotropy of the membrane with 2 distributed properties as a function of the x-sectional area concentration a.

Fig. 2. (Top) Anisotropic strain results for bat wing tissue. (Bottom) PIC used to obtain full field deformation measurements of the sub-surface fibers.

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